

Effect of Flashcards-Mathematical-Game on Interest in Geometry Concepts among Junior Secondary School Mathematics Students in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of flashcards mathematical games on junior secondary school students' interest in geometry in Eket Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. Two research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. Quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pretest posttest non-equivalent control group was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of all government coeducational Junior Secondary School class two (JSS2) students during the 2024/2025 academic session in Eket LGA. A sample of 79 JS 2 students (35 male and 44 female) drawn from intact classes in two randomly selected secondary schools was used for the study. Geometry Interest Scale (GIS) was used as instrument for data collection. The instrument was subjected to face and content validity. The reliability of the instruments was established using Cronbach Alpha with a reliability coefficient of 0.77. Mean, standard deviation was used to answer research questions and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) to test the hypotheses. Results revealed that the use of flashcards mathematical game was more effective in enhancing students' interest in geometry. Also, there was no significant difference on male and female students' interest when taught the concept of geometry in mathematics using flashcards mathematical games. The study concluded that the use of flashcards as instructional game in teaching and learning the concept of geometry was found to be effective in enhancing students' interest without bias to gender. The study recommended that Mathematics teachers should utilize mathematical game such as flashcards in teaching to capture the attention of the students in learning mathematics.

Keyword: flashcards, interest, geometry, gender

Introduction

The need to understand and be able to use mathematics in everyday life and in the workplace continues to increase. Mathematics occupies a crucial and unique role in the human societies and represents a strategic key in the development of the whole mankind. The role of mathematics in the development of the society can clearly be seen in areas of computing, science and technology, social organizations and in the geometrical understanding of space and time. Ndubisi and Ekwueme (2018) defined Mathematics as a creation of human mind, which basically is concerned with ideas, processes and reasoning. Ndubisi and Ekwueme (2018) also described it as the study of measurements, relationships and properties of quantities and sets; hence, its list of definitions is in exhaustive.

Mathematics is of immense importance to national development, which is why the national policy on education has given it the status of a core (compulsory) subject at the primary and secondary levels of education in Nigeria. The themes of the current Mathematics curriculum for senior secondary school are based on five-pronged topics as follows: Number and numeration, Algebraic processes, Geometry, Statistics and Introductory calculus (National Educational Research Development Council NERDC, 2017). Among the themes mentioned, West African Examinations Council (WAEC) through the Chief Examiner's Report (2020), observed that the percentage of students who failed Mathematics at the senior secondary certificate Examination (SSCE) was attributed to poor attempt on Geometry related questions.

Geometry is a prominent branch of mathematics and forms an integral part of most of the school curricula all over the world taking into account its considerable benefits and applications to real life situations. In Nigeria's Educational system, geometry forms an essential part of the mathematics curriculum from the basic to the secondary school levels. Historically,

geometry is probably one of the oldest branches of mathematics. In its historical trends of development, geometry involves the relationship between lengths, areas and volumes of physical objects (Abasi, 2024).

One of the major objectives of geometry instruction is to help children develop an understanding of “geometric shapes and structures and to analyze their characteristics and relationships” (National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM, 2015). The fundamental skills such as reasoning, proving, problem solving, communication, making connections, creative and innovative thinking, and inquiry can be enhanced and fostered by geometry learning (NCTM, 2015). Geometry is a vital component of many aspects of life from practical measurement and construction to styles of living and comfort (Splash Learn, 2023). As innovation in the school curriculum is emphasized, applications of geometric knowledge are highly emphasized in the development of science and technology. Even within classroom instruction, students benefit from not only geometry and measurement skills but also from the specific content areas of the subject.

In spite of the importance of geometry and mathematics as a whole, students’ performance in both internal and external examinations have remained poor and unsatisfactory (Omoro & Adiri, 2019). Elekwa (2015) remarked that students exhibit nonchalant attitude towards mathematics, even when they know that they need it to forge ahead in their academic pursuit and in life. Such students who have already conditioned their minds that mathematics is the most difficult subject are usually not serious in learning of mathematics and thus perform poorly in mathematics assessments. It has been noted that a lot of students struggle with the subject of mathematics, which has a negative impact on their academic performance (Hazarika, 2020). This is largely due to a lack of interest, poor comprehension, and ineffective instructional approaches to mention but a few (Aliakbari & Faraji, 2017).

According to Abasi (2018b), the deplorable state of mathematics achievement is attributed to a number of factors ranging from teacher’s incompetency on the subject matter, learners’ attitude and perception, instructional strategies and materials as well as availability and utilization of mathematics laboratory kits. For a successful mathematics instruction to take place, it is pertinent that every mathematics teacher should engage the students actively with concrete materials to aid the teaching and learning process (Abasi, 2018a). This may help to build confidence in the mind of those who before now have formed within themselves that “mathematics is not for them”. Mathematics is an activity subject as such the way it is being taught is important in helping students to acquire basic mathematical knowledge, skills and attitude to solving different human problems. It is expected that the instructor should use appropriate teaching methods that will offer students ample opportunity to be actively involved during teaching and learning session (Ozomadu & Edeoga, 2022). In this respect, teachers have been advised to use/combine teaching methods, approaches and/or instructional resources that would enhance students’ interest in the learning of mathematics thereby resulting to better performance (Ado & Abasi, 2014).

Due to peculiarities, researchers in mathematics education Ado and Abasi (2021); Abasi and Ado (2021); Edoho, Asuquo, Anditung, and Abasi (2020); Abasi and Umoinyang (2020); Ado, Abasi and Nwankwo (2017) and other prominent stakeholders, like Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN) and Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) have in recent times been beaming their search light on innovative pedagogies that could enhance the effectiveness of teaching and learning mathematics. However, none of these research efforts have been able to resolve this trend. According to Abasi (2024), an instructional situation whereby the student is featured as the active participant while the teacher assumes the roles of a facilitator, mediator and assessor of learning have been found to be superior in developing students’ abilities in applying concepts to personal growth, developing positive attitudes, fostering motivation, and encouraging appropriate cognitive skills. Abasi, Okri and Arikpo (2022) stated that the teaching and learning of Mathematics in general and geometry specifically, requires the discovery of innovative instructional resources that will boost students’ cognitive reasoning thereby enhancing their spatial ability. In the words of Abasi, et. al (2022), the teaching of geometry in mathematics should involve activities that give room for students to think or reason about what they are doing in order to look for relationships, which may enlarge and build a store of mathematical techniques. Therefore, feasible ways of improving the interest of students in mathematics remain the main thrust of this present research.

One key factor that has gained considerable attention in recent years is students’ interest in mathematics. Interest, defined as the level of engagement, curiosity, and enjoyment students experience when interacting with mathematical concepts, has been recognized as a critical component of academic achievement and motivation in various educational contexts (Ryan, Fitzmaurice & O’Donoghue, 2022). Research suggests that students who are genuinely interested in mathematics are more likely to invest time and effort in learning, exhibit higher levels of persistence when faced with challenging problems, and demonstrate better academic performance and retention compared to their less interested peers (Adigun, 2018). Understanding the relationship between interest and academic performance in mathematics is crucial for educators, policymakers, and stakeholders involved in shaping educational practices and curriculum development. By identifying factors that influence students’ interest in mathematics and exploring how it correlates with students’ learning outcomes, educators can design more

effective teaching strategies, interventions, and support mechanisms to enhance students' learning experiences and performance in mathematics (Abid & Noori, 2023). The effectiveness of students' learning outcomes can vary significantly among individuals and is influenced by a variety of factors, including the learning environment, teaching methodologies, individual learning styles, and the nature of the material being learned. However, students' interest could be aroused and enhanced through the use of an appropriate instructional approaches (Umoetuk & Akpan, 2023; Osemwinyen, 2019; Edoho & Abasi 2019). This study seeks to assess the effectiveness of flashcards mathematical game in enhancing students' interest in geometry.

Flashcards are versatile instructional tool used for memorization and learning effectiveness. They consist of cards with information on one side and corresponding details on the other, aiding in memory retention through active recall (Umanah & Sunday, 2022, Chen & Chan, 2019). The use of flashcards has been highlighted as a modern and engaging approach to learning, with studies indicating that flashcards can enhance students' self-regulatory capacity and provide opportunities for more systematic learning (Xodabande *et al.*, 2022; Boroughani *et al.*, 2023). The use of flashcards facilitates students' involvement in the classwork by sharing answers, participating in the lesson, interacting with each other, utilizing the new words and potentially increasing their interest in the learning process (Umanah & Sunday, 2022, Sharmin & Chow, 2020;). The convenience and interactivity of digital flashcards make them appealing to students, potentially increasing their interest and engagement in the learning process (Umanah & Sunday, 2022, Sharmin & Chow, 2020). This study will investigate the efficiency of flashcards in arousing students' interest and enhancing academic performance when used to teach Mathematical concepts especially geometry. Gender is also one of the factors that has influence students' academic performance especially in a science subject like mathematics. Umanah and Sunady (2022) refer to gender as a psychological term describing behavior and attributes expected of individuals, on the basis of being male or female. Therefore, gender is a psychological term and a cultural constant developed by society to differentiate between the roles, behavior, mental and emotional attributes of males and females. The misconception about Mathematics is the notion that Mathematics is about formula and computation that need to be memorized. This view has trifled and thwarted the efforts of students more than anything else. This misconception has moved further to identify Mathematics as a male subject in schools in the Nigerian society. The influence of gender on students' interest and performance in Mathematics has remained a controversial and topical issue amongst educationist and psychologists. The importance of examining educational construct in relation to gender is based mainly on the socio-cultural differences between girls and boys. In view of the fact that gender may have influence on students' interest and academic achievement, inconsistent findings have been made on gender differences and with respect to students' interest and academic achievement in mathematics. It is against this background that the study seeks to investigate the effect of flashcards mathematical game on students' interest in geometry in Eket Local Government Area.

All nation's economic and technological growth is built on the basis of Mathematics. It is believed that without Mathematics, no modern technology can exist, which is why mathematics is made a compulsory subject in Nigerian primary and secondary schools. Hence, failure of Mathematics at all levels of education in Nigeria is a big challenge to the nation. Lack of interest and fear of Mathematics are hindrances to passing examination in the subject (Ado & Abasi, 2014). Despite the relative importance of Mathematics in science and information-based courses, as well as in medicine and social science, students' performance in the subject in both internal and external examinations have remained inconsistent (Abasi, 2024). Students' shortcomings in Mathematics especially geometry emanates from poor fundamental knowledge on the subject particularly basic geometric shapes and concepts, brought about mostly by the lack of appropriate methods of instruction capable of arousing learners' interest and enhancing their performance (WAEC, 2020). According to reports from the WAEC Chief Examiners (Mathematics) May/June 2021 SSCE, students either avoided or failed geometry-related questions. Feasible ways towards solving this problem has been the concern of mathematics educators and researchers. It is evident from literature that the use of flashcards may boost students' interest in mathematics positively. Yet there is dearth of studies in this area, particularly in Akwa Ibom State and so it becomes imperative for this study to provide answer to the question: could the use of flashcards mathematical game have positive effect on students' interest in Mathematics in junior secondary schools in Eket Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State?

Objectives of the study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate on the effect of flashcards mathematical game on junior secondary school students' interest in geometry in Eket Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. In specific terms, the study seeks to:

1. Determine the difference in the mean interest scores of junior secondary school students taught the concept geometry using flashcards mathematical game and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Eket Local Government, Akwa Ibom State.

2. Examine the difference in the mean interest scores of male and female junior secondary school students taught the concept geometry using flashcards mathematical game and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Eket Local Government, Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the conduct of the study.

1. What is the difference in the mean interest scores of junior secondary school students taught the concept geometry using flashcards mathematical game and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Eket Local Government, Akwa Ibom State?
2. What difference exist in the mean interest scores of male and female junior secondary school students taught the concept geometry using flashcards mathematical game and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Eket Local Government, Akwa Ibom State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated for the study.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of junior secondary school students taught the concept geometry using flashcards mathematical game and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Eket Local Government, Akwa Ibom State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of male and female junior secondary school students taught the concept geometry using flashcards mathematical game and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Eket Local Government, Akwa Ibom State

Methodology

Quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pretest posttest non-equivalent control group was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of all government Junior Secondary School class two (JSS2) students during the 2024/2025 academic session in Eket Local Government Area Akwa Ibom State with an enrolment of 1663 students from 10 secondary schools. 79 (35 Male and 44 Female) JSS2 students constitutes the sample size from the target population. The sample size was arrived at by selecting 2 government secondary schools in the area of study using simple random sampling on the basis of being a coeducational and government owned secondary school. The sample schools were explored using an intact class.

Geometry Interest Scale (GIS) was used as instrument for data collection. The instrument consisted of twenty (20) item statements on a four points likert-options constructed by the researcher to measure students' interest in geometry. The instrument was content validated by two experts in measurement and evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was established through a trial test with an intact class of 50 JSS 2 students who were drawn from a school in the area of the study but not part of the main sample. A reliability coefficient of 0.77 was obtained using Cronbach Alpha estimate.

The researcher had series of sessions with the teachers to educate them on the essence of the study and how to achieve an unbiased and better result. The geometry interest scale questionnaire (GIS) was administered to the students as preGIS before the instructional process commence and collected on the spot by the class teachers and handed over to the researcher. In each of the sampled schools, the JSS2 students were taught geometry by the researcher using flashcards mathematical game as instructional approach. After the instructional process, the instrument was administered to the students again as postGIS and collected back immediately by the teacher and were instantly handed over to the researcher.

Results

Mean, Standard Deviation were used to answer research questions and analysis of covariance statistics to test null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Research Question 1

What is the difference in the mean interest scores of junior secondary school students taught the concept geometry using flashcards mathematical game and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Eket Local Government, Akwa Ibom State?

Table 1: Mean, Standard Deviation and Mean Difference of Students’ Pre-interest and Post-interest Scores based on Treatment groups

Treatment Groups	N	Pre-interest Scores		Post-interest Scores		Mean Difference
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
Flashcards	40	31.05	6.01	54.93	10.74	5.26
Without	39	30.08	4.65	49.67	5.03	

Results in Table 1 revealed that the difference in the mean interest scores of students who were exposed to flashcards and those without when teaching the concept of geometry was 5.26 with those exposed to flashcards having a post interest score of 54.93 while those without had a post interest scores of 49.67. This results indicates a mean difference between the two groups in favor of those that were exposed to flashcards with a mean difference of 5.26.

Research Question 2

What difference exist in the mean interest scores of male and female junior secondary school students taught the concept geometry using flashcards mathematical game and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Eket Local Government, Akwa Ibom State?

Table 2: Estimated Marginal Post-interest Mean (Adjusted Mean) and Standard Deviation Scores of the Interaction Effect of Instructional Approaches and Gender Using Pre-interest as Covariate.

Treatment Groups	Gender	N	Mean	SD
Flashcards	Male	17	54.88 ^a	10.77
	Female	23	54.96 ^a	10.95
Without	Male	18	49.94 ^a	4.52
	Female	21	49.43 ^a	5.53

a. Covariates appearing in the model are evaluated at the following values: Pre-interest = 30.38.

As shown in Table 2, the results of the mean interest scores of male students taught the concept of geometry in mathematics using flashcards and those taught without are 54.88, and 49.94 respectively, while those of their female counterparts are 54.96 and 49.43 respectively. This result indicates that no interaction exists between those taught using flashcards and those taught without since the mean value of male and female students taught using flashcards is higher than that of their male counterparts taught without. Hence there is a mean difference.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of junior secondary school students taught the concept geometry using flashcards mathematical game and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Eket Local Government, Akwa Ibom State.

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Students’ Post-interest Scores Classified by Treatment with Pre-interest as Covariate.

Source of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P
Covariates	Preinterest	149.537	1	149.537	1.774	.186
Main Effects	Instructional approach	716.792	1	358.396	4.251	.017*
Error		9104.716	76	84.303		
Total		336188.000	79			
Corrected Total		10071.687	78			

*= Significant @ p<0.05 probability level

In Table 3, the calculated Probability value (P-value) .017 of the main effects (Instructional approach) is less than the significance level (0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that at P < 0.05, there is significant difference in the mean interest scores of junior secondary school students in mathematics when taught the concept of geometry using flashcards as mathematical game and those taught without.

Hypothesis Two:

There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of male and female junior secondary school students taught the concept geometry using flashcards mathematical game and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Eket Local Government, Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Students' Post-Interest Scores Classified by Gender and Instructional Approaches with Pre-interest as Covariate.

Source		Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P
Covariate	Preinterest	149.537	1	149.537	1.774	.186
Main Effects	Instructional games	716.792	1	358.396	4.251	.017
	Gender	6.241	1	6.241	.074	.786
2-Way Interactions	Instructional approach * Gender	49.439	2	24.719	.293	.746*
Error		9104.716	73	84.303		
Total		336188.000	79			
Corrected Total		10071.687	78			

*= Not significant @ $p < 0.05$ probability level

In Table 4, the calculated Probability value (P-value) .746 of the main effects (instructional approach*gender) is greater than the significance level (0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis is upheld. This implies that at $P > 0.05$, there exist no significant difference in the mean interest scores of male and female junior secondary school students in Mathematics when taught the concept of geometry using flashcards as mathematical game and those taught without.

Discussion of Findings

The findings with regard the difference in the mean interest scores of students in Mathematics when taught the concept of geometry using flashcards and those taught without showed that there is a significant difference in the mean interest scores of students in Mathematics when taught the concept of geometry using flashcards and those taught without. Thus, the use of flashcards in teaching and learning the concept of geometry in Mathematics was more effective in boosting students' interest in the subject more than those that were not exposed to the instructional approach. This result could be attributed to the fact that students taught using flashcards engaged more in hands-on activities which helped in bridging the gap between abstract learning. The use of these instructional approaches as a game-based approach to learning engages students actively, giving them the opportunity to share their thoughts, play with their peers, correct misconceptions and fear always associated to learning Mathematics which resulted in developing and building on already existing passion and interest towards learning Mathematics. The result of this finding is in line with the findings by Ado and Abasi (2014) and Abasi (2024) who showed that students taught using hands-on instructional approaches such as practical approach and origami were better enhanced in their interest towards Mathematics than their counterparts taught without.

The findings with regard the difference in the mean interest scores of male and female junior secondary school students in Mathematics when taught the concept of geometry using flashcards as mathematical game and those taught without showed that there is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of male and female junior secondary school students in Mathematics when taught the concept of geometry using flashcards as mathematical game and those taught without. Thus, the use of these instructional approaches in teaching and learning the concept of geometry in mathematics was not gender bias thereby having an equal effect on both male and female students when taught the concept of geometry in mathematics. Thus, both male and female students benefited equally from the use of these instructional approaches in learning the concept of geometry in mathematics. The result of this finding is in line with the findings by Sani and Salahudeen (2016), Eboka, Uzomah and Onyemenem (2019) and Abasi, Okri and Adie (2022) who showed that there was no significant interaction effect between the teaching approaches and gender on students' academic performance in mathematics.

Conclusion

Based on the results obtained from this study, the researcher concluded that students' exposure to mathematical games as instructional approach in teaching and learning the concept of geometry in Mathematics was found to be most effective in enhancing students' interest without bias to gender. The application of this game as instructional approach in teaching/learning process set up a premise for a fun-filled and play-way learning environment which harnessed students' interest in the subject as compared to those that were not exposed to this experiences.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher considered the following recommendations relevant for the improvement of Mathematics education.

1. Mathematics teachers should effectively utilize mathematical games such as flashcards in teaching the concept of geometry specifically and in the general teaching of Mathematics concepts as it has been proven to enhance students' interest in the subject.
2. Government should make adequate provisions for funding and equipping of school Mathematics laboratories with mathematical kits to promote and encourage the use of Mathematics games in teaching in schools to aid the teacher and students in effective instructional delivery.
3. Government and education administrators should also organize public lectures, seminars and workshops on the use of mathematical games in schools as a way of sensitizing the new concept.

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